

Differential Levels of Grit among Substance Using and Non-Using Youths in Bayelsa State, Nigeria: Implication for Addiction Counselor's Intervention

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 20th Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Differential-levels Grit Substance use Youth Counselors intervention</p>	<p>This study examined differences in grit levels between substance-using and non-using youths in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, and explored the implications for addiction counseling. Using a descriptive comparative design, data were collected from youths using the grit scale and a rapid drug-use testing kit. Descriptive statistics and independent t-test revealed that non-using substance youths demonstrated significantly higher grit scores than substance-using youths, indicating reduced perseverance and goal-directed consistency among those involved in drug use. These findings underscore grit as a relevant psychological variable in understanding vulnerability to substance use and in guiding rehabilitation efforts. The study recommends integrating grit-enhancement strategies such as goal-setting, self-regulation training, and motivational counseling into addiction intervention programs for youths.</p>

1. Introduction

Substance use among youths has become a major public health issue globally, with recent studies showing increasing rates of psychoactive substance use among youths (UNODC, 2023). In Nigeria, the situation is particularly alarming. The first-ever National Drug Use Survey reported that over 14.4% of Nigerians aged 15–64 engage in drug use, a figure significantly higher than the global average (UNODC, 2018). The South–South region, where Bayelsa State is located, has consistently been identified as one of the regions with the highest prevalence of substance use, influenced by socio-economic challenges, peer pressure, and environmental stressors (Nwagu, Nweke & Oji, 2020). Such patterns highlight an urgent need for deeper psychological investigations to understand why some youths resort to substances while others, exposed to similar conditions, do not.

Existing research has established that substance use among youths is shaped not only by environmental and social variables but also by psychological characteristics such as self-regulation, resilience, and impulse control (Wills et al., 2016). One emerging psychological construct receiving increasing attention is grit, which is conceptualized by Duckworth, Peterson, Matthews, and Kelly (2007) as the capacity to sustain effort and interest toward long-term goals despite failures and adversity. Grit has been associated with improved academic performance, higher resilience, and reduced engagement in risky behaviours (Credé, Tynan & Harms, 2017). This suggests that grit may serve as a protective factor against substance use by helping youths withstand peer pressure, delay gratification, and remain focused on positive life pursuits.

However, despite the theoretical relevance of grit, empirical evidence exploring the differential levels of grit between substance-using and non-using youths in Nigeria remains limited. Studies conducted in Western contexts have shown that individuals with lower grit scores are more susceptible to maladaptive coping mechanisms including substance use (Kleiman et al., 2019). Yet, contextual differences such as culture, socioeconomic realities, and stress exposure necessitate local studies, as findings from Western populations cannot be assumed to apply to Bayelsa youths.

In Bayelsa State, youths face unique stressors including unemployment, community-level violence, poverty, oil-related environmental degradation, and the psychological burden of socio-economic instability (Ibaba & Etekpe, 2019). These conditions may diminish perseverance and increase vulnerability to substance use. While some youths succumb to these stressors, others remain goal-driven, resilient, and abstain from drug use—indicating that psychological strengths such as grit may differentiate these groups. Unfortunately, addiction counseling programmes in Bayelsa State largely focus on behavioural modification and relapse prevention, with insufficient emphasis on enhancing internal traits such as perseverance and goal-directed resilience. Without empirical evidence on grit differences, counselors lack evidence-based guidance for designing tailored strength-oriented interventions.

This study therefore seeks to address this important gap by examining the differential levels of grit among substance-using and non-using youths in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Findings from this investigation will provide critical insight into whether grit plays a significant role in youths' susceptibility or resistance to substance use. Such evidence is essential for strengthening addiction counseling interventions through approaches that build perseverance, motivation, and long-term goal orientation. Ultimately, this study aims to contribute to improved substance use prevention strategies and more effective rehabilitation programmes for youths in Bayelsa State.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Concept of Grit

Grit is defined as perseverance and passion for long-term goals, reflecting an individual's ability to persist despite challenges or failures (Duckworth et al., 2007). It refers to maintaining passion and perseverance toward the highest-level goal for several years or decades, even when facing disappointment and frustration (Duckworth and Gross, 2014). Grit has been associated with academic achievement, life satisfaction, reduced engagement in risky behaviours, and improved mental health (Credé, Tynan & Harms, 2017). Youths with high grit are more likely to delay gratification, resist peer pressure, and stay committed to positive goals.

2.2 Concept of Substance Use

Substance use refers to the consumption of psychoactive substances such as alcohol, cannabis, tramadol, codeine mixtures, inhalants, sedatives, and stimulants which alters mood, cognition, and behaviour (UNODC, 2023). In Nigeria, the National Drug Use Survey reported an alarming rise in the use of cannabis, tramadol, and pharmaceutical opioids among youths aged 15–34 years (UNODC, 2018). Bayelsa State, part of the South–South geopolitical zone, shows a high prevalence of youth involvement drug use due to socio-economic deprivation, environmental stressors, peer influence, and weak parental monitoring (Nwagu, Nweke & Oji, 2020; Morufu et al., 2019).

2.3 Youth Vulnerability to Substance Use

Youth-hood is a developmental period marked by experimentation, identity formation, and heightened susceptibility to peer influence. Factors such as unemployment, poverty, family instability, academic pressure, and stress related to socio-environmental degradation in the South-South increases youths vulnerability to substance use (Ibaba & Etekpe, 2019). Poor self-regulation, low resilience, and weak goal orientation have also been identified as predictors of youth involvement in risky behaviours (Wills et al., 2016).

2.4 Relevance of Grit to Substance Use

Grit plays an important role in perseverance, self-control and long-term decision-making which are some of the major factors essential for resisting substance use. Individuals low in perseverance may adopt substance use as a coping mechanisms when faced with stress or adversity (Kleiman et al., 2019). Conversely, those with high grit are better able to maintain focus on long-term goals, making them less likely to engage in high risk behaviours such as substance use. This suggests that grit may differentiate substance-using from non-using youths.

2.5 Theoretical Review

2.5.1 Grit Theory

Duckworth's Grit theory posits that success in long-term pursuits depends more on sustained effort and passion than on innate talent or intelligence (Duckworth et al., 2007). Grit Theory supports the idea that perseverance is a psychological buffer against maladaptive behaviours, including substance abuse. Because grit is partially malleable, it can be strengthened through interventions thus making it useful for addiction counselors.

2.5.2 Self-Regulation Theory

Self-Regulation theory explains how individuals control their thoughts, emotions, and behaviours to achieve goals (Baumeister et al., 2007). Substance use is often linked to deficits in self-regulation, impulsivity, and poor emotional control. Grit aligns with this theory because perseverance involves self-discipline, delay of gratification, and long-term focus. Strengthening self-regulation may therefore increase grit and reduce susceptibility to substance use (Quinn, et al. 2022).

2.5.3 Social Cognitive Theory

Bandura's Social Cognitive theory emphasizes reciprocal interactions among behaviour, personal factors, and the environment (Bandura, 1986). Self-efficacy, a core component of the theory, influences a person's ability and build confidence in self to resist temptations such as substance use. Grit supports self-efficacy by reinforcing resilience and persistence when faced with challenges. From this theoretical lens, addiction counselors can use modelling, skill-building, and reinforcement strategies to enhance grit in clients.

2.6 Empirical Review

Research exploring the link between grit and risky or addictive behaviours is still emerging but shows promising patterns. Several clinical and community studies report that higher grit (particularly the perseverance-of-effort facet) is associated with lower engagement in some risky behaviours and better treatment outcomes among people with substance-use problems. For example,

Griffin et al, (2016) found that grit measures showed acceptable psychometric properties in samples of patients with substance use disorders and that grit correlated with measures of adaptive functioning, suggesting grit may relate to recovery-relevant capacities. A study on whether grit matters by Han and Hwang (2025) found that, adolescents with higher grit levels were less likely to engage in drinking behaviors. After controlling for interpersonal and cultural/environmental-level factors, a higher level of grit was associated with a reduced chance of drinking behavior among adolescents. Population and school-based research also suggest grit can act as a protective factor against substance use and delinquent behaviours. Guerrero et al (2016) reviewed adolescent data indicating grit is negatively associated with several externalizing and risk behaviours, and proposed grit as a protective factor for adolescent substance use and related risks. Controlled interventions which explicitly train perseverance and self-regulation (grit-focused programmes) have shown improvements in wellbeing and some substance-related outcomes among youth in treatment settings, though evidence is still limited and effect sizes vary.

Context-specific empirical work in Nigeria and Bayelsa State supports the premise that adolescent and youth substance use is a pressing local problem shaped by multi-level factors (poverty, unemployment, peer networks, environmental stressors) but there is a notable scarcity of studies that directly examine intrapersonal protective traits such as grit within Nigerian samples. Community and school surveys in Bayelsa and other states in the South-South zone documents high prevalence of alcohol, tramadol, codeine mixtures and cannabis use among youths. Some of these studies identify low supervision, peer influence, ignorance and stress exposure as correlates factors. Published empirical comparisons of grit between substance-using and non-using youths in Bayelsa are, to date, essentially absent creating the exact research gap this study addresses (Morufu et al, 2019).

3. Methodology

3.1 Sample

A total sample size of 74 youths attending community security recruitment exercise in Yenagoa aged between 20-39 years were selected.

3.2 Design

The study utilized a comparative descriptive survey design. This design is suitable because it allows the researcher to compare differences in grit levels between two naturally existing groups- substance using youths and non-using youths without manipulating variables. Participants for this study were chosen as a purposive sample. In addition to the secondary data collected, primary data was collected using two methods: (a) Rapid urine drug testing kits to differentiate between substance users and non-substance users and (b) Grit scale developed by Duckworth et al (2007), using a 5-point Likert format ranging from 1 = *Not at all like me* to 5 = *Very much like me* was used to collect data to determine the grit levels of substance users and non-substance users. The higher scores indicate stronger grit tendencies. A total of seventy four Grit questionnaires (74) were administered to the participants in the field. All the 74 questionnaires were retrieved and found valid for analyses using descriptive statistics and independent samples t-test. Participants received an informed consent document prior to data collection and they were allowed to read it and ask questions for clarification before submitting their signed consent to the research assistants.

4. Results

This section of the research work focuses on how the data garnered from the field were presented and analyzed. Data for this study were presented in the table below and further analyzed with the use of descriptive statistics and independent samples t-test.

Table 1: Summary table of descriptive statistics showing grit scores of substance users and non-users

Group	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Drug users	37	1.00	2.00	1.68	0.47
Non-drug users	37	5.00	10.00	5.73	1.73

Source: Researcher's computation (2025)

The results in Table 1: shows that substance users in Bayelsa State recorded grit scores ranging from 1.00 to 2.00, with a mean score of 1.68 and a standard deviation of 0.47. This indicates that substance users generally exhibit very low grit, with little variability in their grit levels. On the other hand, non-substance users recorded grit scores ranging from 5.00 to 10.00, with a mean score of 5.73 and a standard deviation of 1.73. This suggests that non-substance users have substantially higher grit levels compared to substance users, with a moderate spread of scores reflecting greater individual differences.

This finding is consistent with previous studies which suggest that individuals with higher grit scores are less likely to engage in risky behaviors, including substance use (Han and Hwang, 2025). This result is also similar to previous studies which reported that grit was a protective factor against substance abuse among Latino and Israeli adolescents and young adults (Guerrero et al. 2016). Low grit can be linked to low motivation, reduced self-control, and poor capacity to handling psychosocial challenges such as unemployment, family instability, or environmental pressures. These factors can interfere with their ability to pursue meaningful goals or persist in the face of obstacles thus turning to substance use.

4.1 Inferential Statistics

To determine whether the observed difference in grit levels between substance users and non-users is statistically significant, an independent samples t-test (Welch's t-test) was conducted. The result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Independent Samples t-Test Comparing Grit Levels

Comparison group	t-value	p-value	Decision
Substance user's vs Non-substance users	-13.77	4.69×10^{-17}	Significant

Source: Researcher's computation (2025)

The t-test result revealed a statistically significant difference between the grit levels of substance users and non-substance users in Bayelsa State, $t = -13.77$, $p < .001$. This indicates that non-substance users possess significantly higher grit levels than substance users. The extremely small p-value suggests that the observed difference is highly unlikely to have occurred by chance. The large difference reinforces the idea that grit plays a major role in differentiating those who engage in substance use from those who do not. Previous studies reveal that higher grit may act as a protective factor, helping individuals resist peer pressure, persist through adversity, and maintain healthier lifestyles (Wills et al., 2016). Conversely, lower grit may increase vulnerability to risky behaviors, including substance abuse. This finding suggests that psychological constructs such as grit should be considered when designing intervention and rehabilitation programs.

5. Conclusion

This study examined the difference in grit levels between substance users and non-substance users in Bayelsa State. To determine the difference, the study employed descriptive statistics and independent samples t-test. Results of the study indicates that substance users generally possess lower grit levels and that individuals who abstain from substance use tend to have higher grit levels. The study concludes that grit is a meaningful predictor of drug use behavior, and strengthening grit may play an important role in drug prevention and rehabilitation efforts in Bayelsa State.

6. Recommendations

The researchers recommend as follows:

- (i). Rehabilitation centers in Bayelsa state should introduce activities that help improve perseverance, goal-setting, and resilience. This may include intentional counseling, skills training, mentorship programs, and structured goal-setting exercises.
- (ii). Government and non-governmental organizations should create programs that provide economic and social support to vulnerable youths such as employment opportunities, sports programs, and any other youth empowerment initiatives to foster long-term goal commitment.

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References

- [1] Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- [2] Baumeister, R. F., & Vohs, K. D. (2007). Self-regulation, ego depletion, and motivation. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 1(1), 115–128. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9004.2007.00001>
- [3] Credé, M., Tynan, M. C., & Harms, P. D. (2017). Much ado about grit: A meta-analytic synthesis of the grit literature. *J Pers Soc Psychol*, 113, (3)492-511. doi: 10.1037/pspp000102.
- [4] Duckworth, A., & Gross J. J.(2014). Self-Control and Grit: Related but Separable Determinants of Success. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 23(5),319–325. 10.1177/0963721414541462.
- [5] Duckworth, A. L. , Peterson C., Matthews M. D., & Kelly D. R.(2007). Grit: Perseverance and Passion for Long-Term Goals. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 92(6), 1087–1101. 10.1037/0022-3514.92.6.1087.
- [6] Griffin, M.L., McDermott, K.A., McHugh, K., Fitzmaurice, G.M., & Weiss, R.D.(2016). Grit in Patients with Substance Use Disorders. *Am J Addict.*, 25(8), 652–658. doi:10.1111/ajad.12460.
- [7] Guerrero, L. R., Dudovitz R., Chung, P. J., Dosanjh, K. K., & Wong, M. D.(2016). Grit: A Potential protective factor against substance use and other risk behaviors among Latino adolescents. *Academic Pediatrics*, 16(3), 275–281. 10.1016/j.acap.2015.12.016.
- [8] Han, Y., & Hwang, Y. (2025). Does Grit Matter? The Relationship between grit and drinking behavior among adolescents: A Cross-sectional study of a nationally representative sample of Korean adolescents. *J Nurs Scholarsh*, 57(4), 587–596. doi: 10.1111/jnu.70007.
- [9] Ibaba, I. S., & Etekepe, A. (2019). Youth restiveness and socio-economic development challenges in the Niger Delta. *Journal of Social and Policy Issues*, 16(1), 44–59.
- [10] Kleiman, E. M., Yeager, A. L., Grove, J. L., Kellerman, J. K., & Kim, J. S. (2019). Grit and over commitment: Associations with suicidal ideation and substance use. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 49(2), 620–633. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sltb.12463>

- [11] Morufu, R.M., Funmilayo, A.A., Okoyen, M.I.E., & Oyinlola, B.O.(2019). Public health impact of substance use on adolescent: A snapshot of Yenagoa in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *Am J Biomed Sci & Res.*, 4(3). 000796. DOI: 10.34297/
- [12] Nwagu, E. N., Nweke, A. N., & Oji, O. (2020). Prevalence and socio-demographic correlates of drug use among youths in the South–South region of Nigeria. *Journal of Substance Use*, 25(6), 638–645.
- [13] Nawi, A. M., Ismail, R., Ibrahim, F., Hassan, M. R., Abdul Manaf, M. R., Amit, N., Ibrahim, N., & Shafurdin, N. S. (2021). Risk and protective factors of drug abuse among adolescents: A systematic review. *BMC Public Health*, 21(1), 2088. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-11906-2>
- [14] Quinn, C. A., Walter, Z. C., de Andrade, D., Dingle, G., Haslam, C., & Hides, L. (2022). Controlled trial examining the strength-based Grit Wellbeing and Self-Regulation Program for young people in residential settings for substance use. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(21), 13835. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192113835>
- [15] United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2018). *Drug Use Survey in Nigeria 2018: Research Report*. UNODC.
- [16] United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2023). *World Drug Report 2023*. UNODC.
- [17] Wills, T. A., Pokhrel, P., Morehouse, E., & Fenster, B. (2016). Behavioral and emotional regulation and adolescent substance use problems: A test of moderation effects. *Psychology of Addictive Behaviors*, 25(2), 279–292.